

SIRAVEDHA-A LITERARY REVIEW**Dr. Kirti Dudhe*¹, Dr. Laxminivas R. Soni²**Pg Schlor (Shalyatantra)¹, HOD and Professor²

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ABSTRACT

Father of ancient surgery, Acharya Sushruta has mentioned various method of Raktmokshana i.e Shringa, Jalauka and Alabu etc. Siravedha is one of them. Full description of Siravedha has been given by Acharya Sushruta in Sushruta Samhita Sharira Sthana chapter 8. All the Siras carries all doshas in the body. There is no Sira in the body which carries either the Vayu, the Pitta or the Kapha therefore Siras should be considered as Sarvavaha. According to ayurveda, disease is the result of prakupita doshas. Siravedha, letting out noxious blood from the body and it will cure the disease or otherwise it will make a clear pathway towards further treatment modalities. Siravedha is the independent procedure or treatment to cure many diseases like gradhasi (sciatica), gout, varicose pain, skin diseases etc.

सिराव्यधसिसित्साधध शल्यतंत्रे प्रीसतधतः ॥ ि. शा 8/23

Siravedha is the half treatment of Shalya Tantra. According to Acharya Sushruat there are 700 Siras in our body but basic Siras are mainly 40. Origin of 40 Siras is nabhi and divided into, vatta, pitta, kapha and rakta. There are 98 Avedhya Siras in our body they should not be puncture, if punctured then it will cause the disability or even death.

KEYWORDS: Siravedha, avedhya sira, sarvavaha, raktmokshana, doshas.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is a well-established and ancient system of medicine, renowned for its distinctive contributions to Shalya Tantra. With a continuous history of evolution spanning more than

3000 years, this science has been enriched through various commentaries authored over different periods. However, due to historical disturbances and generational transitions, many of these classical concepts have become misinterpreted or less clearly understood, and therefore require more comprehensive study and reinterpretation. Acharya Sushruta has emphasized the importance of Siravyadha—a specialized form of Raktamokshana—by describing it as Ardha-Chikitsa (half of all therapeutic measures) within Shalya Tantra. Raktamokshana, one of the five principal Panchakarma procedures, represents a fundamental detoxification technique. The term is derived from the words “Rakta” (blood) and “Mokshana” (to expel), together meaning “the removal or letting out of blood. Raktamokshana (bloodletting)^[1] Can be broadly classified into two categories:

1. Ashastra (performed with the measures other than sharp instruments)
2. Jalauka (leech)
3. Alabu (bottle guard)
4. Shringa (horn)
5. Sashastra (performed with sharp instrument)
6. Prachhana (scarification)
7. Siravedha (venepuncture)

Indications^[2]

1. Five types of Vidradhi (abscess) except Sannipataj Vidradhi
2. Kushtha (skin diseases)
3. Ekdeshaj Shotha (edema at a single site)
4. Shleepada (filariasis)
5. Poisoning
6. Arbuda (tumor)
7. Granthi (swelling)
8. Updansha (chancroid)
9. Stanaroga (diseases of breast)
10. Gridhrasi (sciatica)
11. Vatarakta (gout).

Contraindications^[3]

1. Ksheena (lean and thin, malnourished)
2. Pandu (Anaemia)

3. Kasa, Swash, Shosha, Jwar
4. Upwas, Pakshaghat, Pipasa, Murcha
5. Garbhini (pregnant woman)
6. Bala, Vriddha, Ruksha, Bhiru
7. After Panch Karma

APPROPRIATE TIME^[4]

1. Varsha rutu (rainy season)-When sky is clear that is without clouds and rain.
2. Grishma rutu (summer season)-When the environment is cool that is in the morning hours.
3. Hemanta rutu (winter season)-Madhyahana (afternoon time)

Pramaana^[5] (Quantity of Bloodletting)

In strong individuals with high Doṣha accumulation and in suitable middle age, one Prastha of blood may be allowed to flow.

1 Prastha in Shodhana procedures (Vamana, Virechana, Raktamokṣaṇa): 13.5 Pala ≈ 540 ml. 1 Prastha in general drug dosage context: 16 Pala ≈ 640 ml.

According to Sharangdhara & Bhavaprakasa

Uttama – 1 Prastha Madhyama – ½ Prastha Hina – ¼ Prastha

Complete removal of all vitiated blood is not recommended.

Remaining Doṣha-contaminated blood should be treated with Samana (palliative) therapies.

Sthana-bheda Anusara Siravedha (Site-based Guidelines)

In maṃsala pradesa (muscular areas)

Puncture size should be equal to one Yava (barley grain).

In less muscular regions, puncture size should be half Yava or one Vrihi (rice grain).

Instrument used: Bṛhimukha Sastra (broad puncturing tool).

In veins located over bones

Puncture size: half Yava.

Instrument used: Kutharika Sastra (small axe-shaped too)

PROCEDURE^[1,6]

Pre-procedure Preparation

1. The patient selected for Siravedha should be given light liquid food or Yavagu prior to the procedure.

2. Snehana (oleation) and Swedana (fomentation) therapies should be performed to prepare the body.
3. The physician should arrange all required instruments and emergency medicines in advance to manage any intra- or post-procedure complications.
4. The patient should be seated comfortably, preferably facing the east direction.
5. The puncture site must be thoroughly cleaned to ensure it is free from dust, dirt, or any contaminants.
6. A cloth is traditionally tied one finger-breadth above the puncture site; however, in modern practice, a tourniquet is commonly used.
7. The chosen vein should be made prominent before puncturing.

Procedure

1. The vein is punctured with a needle in a single, steady stroke—neither too slow nor too forceful—to allow blood to flow freely.
2. Initially, the vitiated blood emerges, typically darker in color, indicating the removal of impure blood.

Post-procedure Care

1. The flow and total amount of blood are carefully monitored.
2. When Siravedha is performed correctly, the blood flow naturally ceases after some time.
3. If the quantity reaches approximately one Prastha, the flow is stopped using a pressure bandage.
4. The patient is advised to rest for a few minutes following completion of the procedure.

Samyaka viddha lakshana^[7]

1. Laghava (feeling of lightness in body)
2. Vedana shanti (relief in pain)
3. Vyadhivegaparikshaya (relief in concerned disease)
4. Manaprasada (feeling of wellness in mind)

Atiyoga Lakshana^[8]

Symptoms of excessive blood flow

1. Aandhya (blindness)
2. Timira (blackouts in front of eyes)
3. Akshepaka (seizures)

4. Pakshaghata (paralysis)
5. Trishna (thirst)
6. Daha (burning sensation)
7. Marana (death)

This is observed practically also that many times post trauma, the main cause of death is excessive blood loss.

Siravedha According to Diseases^[9]

Pada Daha (burning sensation in soles), Pada Harsha (tingling/tenderness), Chip (whitlow), Visarpa (erysipelas), Vata Shonita (gout), Vata Kantaka (ankle sprain), Vicharchika (skin disorder), Pada Daari (fissures of soles):-Puncture the vein located 2 Angula (\approx 4 cm) above Chipra Marma using a Vrihimukha Sastra (trocar/thick needle).

1. Shleepada (Filariasis)

Vata dominance: puncture the vein 4 Angula above Gulpha Sandhi (ankle joint). Pitta dominance: puncture the vein below the ankle.

Kapha dominance: puncture the prominent vein of the big toe.

2. Apachi (neck swelling/tumor): Puncture 2 Angula below Indravasti Marma.

3. Kostrukashirsha (knee inflammation), Khanjata, Pangulya (lameness), Vata Vedana:Puncture in the Jagha region, 4 Angula above the ankle joint.

4. Gridhrasi (sciatica), Vishvachi (arm pain):Vein puncture 4 Angula above or below the Jaanu Sandhi.

5. Galganda (neck tumor/goiter): Puncture the vein located at the root (base) of the thigh.

6. Pliharoga (spleen disorders): Puncture the vein on the left arm, Inner side of the elbow joint in Midline of the arm Or between the ring and little finger.

7. Yakrit Daludar (liver disorders), Kaphodara (Kapha-type abdominal enlargement): Puncture in the right arm at the same sites as for Pliharoga.
Same site used even in cough and dyspnea.

8. Pravahika (dysentery), Shoola (abdominal pain):Puncture 2 Angula above the symphysis pubis.

9. Parivartika, Upadansha, Shukra-dosha (penile disorders/semen disorders):Puncture the middle vein of the penis.

10. Mutra Vriddhi (hydrocele):Puncture the veins on the lateral sides of the scrotum.

11. Dakodara (ascites): Puncture 4 Angula left to the umbilical raphe, below the umbilicus.

12. Antarvidradhi (internal abscess), Parshva Shoola (flank pain): Puncture between the axilla and breast on the left flank.
13. Bahushosha (arm wasting), Avabahuka (frozen shoulder): Puncture between the two shoulders.
14. Tritiyaka Jwara (tertian fever): Puncture at the midline of the Trika (lumbosacral region).
15. Chaturthaka Jwara (quartan fever): Puncture below the shoulder joint, on any one side.
16. Apasmara (epilepsy): Puncture the vein located near the lower jaw joint, close to the ear.
17. Unmada (insanity): Puncture at, Temple region, Hairline border, Chest or Outer angle of eyes Forehead
18. Jihva & Danta Roga (tongue and dental disorders): Puncture below the tongue (Adho-jihva).
19. Taalu Roga (palate disorders): Puncture at the palate (Taaluu).
20. Karna Roga (ear disorders) & Karna Shoola (ear pain): Puncture above the ear.
21. Gandha Agrahana (loss of smell), Nasa Roga: Puncture at the tip of the nose.
22. Timir (early blindness), Akshipaka (eye inflammation): Puncture at the base of the nose, forehead, or outer angle of the eye.
23. Diseases of the head & Adhimantha: Same puncture sites as above (nose base, forehead, outer eye angle).

Measurement Note

1 Angula = 2 cm.

Dusta Siravedha^[10,11]

(Improper Venepuncture) – 20 Types

1. Durviddha: Minute sharp puncture; blood flow invisible; pain and swelling present.
2. Atividdha: Excessively deep puncture; blood flows excessively or internally.
3. Kunchita: Similar to Atividdha.
4. Pichchita: Puncture made with a blunt instrument; vein becomes thickened.
5. Kuttita: Repeated puncturing; no blood flow; vein injured by the instrument.
6. Aprasrita: No blood flow due to cold, fear, or fainting.
7. Atyudirna: Puncture caused by a sharp, thick instrument.
8. Anteviddha: Very scanty blood flow.
9. Parisushka: Vein depleted of blood, filled with air.
10. Kunita: Only one-fourth of the vein punctured; minimal blood flow.

11. Vepita: Improper binding or trembling hand; causes body tremors and fainting.
12. Anutthita Viddha: Similar to Vepita.
13. Shastrahata: Vein is cut; leads to excessive bleeding and loss of function of the part.
14. Tiryak Viddha: Instrument inserted obliquely from the side of the vein.
15. Apaviddha: Using the instrument without making a puncture.
16. Avyadhya: Attempted puncture without proper use of instrument.
17. Vidruta: Puncture done when physician is mentally unsteady.
18. Dhenuka: Striking the body part repeatedly to raise the vein, causing repeated bleeding.
19. Punah-punar Viddha: Vein punctured multiple times due to use of a very fine instrument.

General warning

Puncturing ligaments, bones, joints, major veins, or fatal spots may cause pain, swelling, deformity, or even death.

CONCLUSION

Siravedha has demonstrated significant potential in providing relief from various chronic and lifestyle-related disorders. Its therapeutic scope, when applied with proper clinical judgment, highlights its value as an effective treatment modality. Therefore, it should be practiced conscientiously and systematically on a broader patient population with the objective of standardizing and establishing it as a reliable therapeutic procedure within Ayurvedic clinical practice.

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